

Dos and Don'ts - Quick Guide To Interviewing

General approach:

In line with ARRA commitments, the recruitment and interview process at IRB Barcelona should:

- Prioritize qualitative assessment over simplistic quantitative metrics.
- Recognize a broad range of research contributions, including:
 - Scientific rigor and methodological quality
 - Open science practices
 - Mentorship and supervision
 - Team science and collaboration
 - Leadership and research culture
 - Knowledge transfer and societal impact
 - Research integrity and reproducibility
 - Contributions to shared infrastructures and data resources
- Apply transparent, structured, and predefined evaluation criteria.
- Ensure fairness, diversity, and inclusion.
- Consider the context of each candidate's career trajectory.

Remember:

An effective interviewer looks for reasons to qualify a candidate rather than disqualify them. You are representing the IRB Barcelona throughout your interaction. Make a good impression while creating a positive candidate experience! Partner with HR for any questions or assistance.

Dos and Don'ts during the Interview Process:

Dos:

Before

- Find an appropriate interview location and time.
- Address logistical details before the interview regarding location or online, parking arrangements, who the candidate should ask for when arriving for the interview, etc.
- Before the interview, provide candidates with information about interview format, general evaluation approach and panel composition (if applicable).
- Read résumés and other application materials ahead of time, considering career context (mobility and career breaks), individual contributions within collaborative work and contributions to open science and responsible research practices.

- Have a thorough understanding of the position and its requirements.
- Develop questions and identify elements of good answers in advance.
- Review questions to avoid unconscious bias.
- For panels, identify who will lead the interview and coordinate who asks which questions.
- Ensure gender equality in the composition of the recruitment panels.

During

- Start and end the interview on time.
- Introduce yourself and create a welcoming and open environment.
- Provide an overview of the organization and the position.
- Outline the interview format to the candidate.
- Explain how the candidate will be assessed (qualitative and multidimensional approach).
- Ask only job-related questions.
- Use the interview as an opportunity to showcase the highlights of working at the IRB Barcelona.
- Ask the same questions to all candidates for fairness.
- Ask follow-up questions if you do not have a clear understanding of a response or to get more detailed examples.
- Explore:
 - Scientific quality and rigor
 - Specific personal contributions to projects
 - Commitment to research integrity and reproducibility
 - Experience in mentoring and team development
 - Engagement with open science practices
- Give the candidate time to think about past experiences and examples while answering questions.
- Provide the candidate with information about the next steps in the hiring process.
- Remember that the role of a good interviewer is to look for reasons to qualify a candidate rather than disqualify a candidate.

After

- Evaluate the candidate on predetermined criteria soon after the interview.
- Follow up with candidates in a timely matter, even if they are not moving forward in the process. Inform HR of the candidates that are not moving forward in the process so they can send the rejection email.
- Once the position has been closed, write an evaluation report.
- Be available to provide feedback if requested.

Don'ts:

- Don't compare solely by number of publications or journal prestige.
- Don't take extensive notes, which can make the candidate tense up and stop talking.
- Don't ask only questions that can be answered with one word, such as "yes" or "no."
- Don't ask leading questions that prompt the answer you want, such as "We value individuals that can adapt quickly...how well do you adapt to new situations?"
- Don't ask simple questions related to information the candidate has already provided on the CV or cover letter.
- Don't let the interview get off track.
- Don't look impatient or bored.
- Don't forget to ask candidates if they have any questions.
- Don't rush candidates if they struggle to respond to a question. Allow for silence. Offer to come back to the question if needed.
- Don't call for references if the candidate has not provided you the contacts.
- Don't ask questions that are considered discriminatory.

Equal Opportunities

We are an Equal Opportunity Employer and all qualified applicants are considered for employment without regard to race, color, religion, age, sex, sexual orientation, gender identity, nationality or ethnic origin, marital status, number of children that a candidate may have, etc.

Types of Interview Questions:

- **Behavioral:** candidates are asked to describe past behaviors.
 - Describe a time you had to build a partnership to achieve a shared objective.
 - Tell me how you effectively work under pressure, examples? Could you describe the situation.
 - Recall a situation in which you made a mistake while working with others and how you fix it.
 - Describe a time when you challenged an idea or approach.
 - Tell me about a time you went the extra mile for a project or work.
- **Situational:** Candidates are asked to respond to a specific situation they may face on the job.
 - When taking on multiple project with varying deadlines, how would you stay on track?
 - Describe the work environment that would allow you to do your best work.
 - How would you respond to a co-worker who has criticized your approach to solving a problem?
 - How do you communicate a complex process or task to others?
- **Competency:** Candidates are asked questions targeting a specific skill set or competency.
 - **Communication:** Tell us about a time you had to adjust your communication approach

- during a project.
- Leadership: Describe a situation when you assume the role of leader. Were there challenges? How did you address these?
 - Technical: What technical training have you received? Can you provide examples of how you apply it?
 - Collaboration: Tell us about the time you assisted a co-worker with a project. Why and how did you assist?
 - Engagement: What is your definition of employee engagement? Describe your experience in projects related to engagement and the role you played.

<p>Pros for Behavioral & Situational:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Get examples from the past to assess future performance. - Storytelling allows candidates to interview more effectively. - Goes into deeper detail. - Allows for the ability to assess how a candidate 	<p>will react to on the job situations.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Able to understand a candidate's decisionmaking skills. <p>Cons for Behavioral & Situational:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How a candidate solved a problem in the past may not be the way to solve a problem today. 	<p>Pros for Competency:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gives the candidate an opportunity to best understand what you're looking for. - Candidate has an opportunity to outline, explain & demonstrate their qualifications. - Allows the ability to gauge a candidate's knowledge & comfort 	<p>level with competencies.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Easier to prepare questions in a structured manner. <p>Cons for Competency:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If a candidate lacks competencies you seek, it may create an unease feeling in the candidate
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